

1 **Superlubricity of polyethylene glycol solutions: Running-in effects, thickness**
2 **changes, and rheology**

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12 **Abstract:** The role of additives in liquid superlubricity is regarded as a crucial element of the
13 running-in process due to their role in reducing friction. Nevertheless, there has been minor
14 investigation into rheological changes that occur during the process. This paper presents an
15 examination of the evolution of film thickness over time and its subsequent behavior. The
16 primary experiments were performed on an optical ball-on-disk tribometer, with the ability to
17 control the percentage of slip. The film thickness was evaluated by optical interferometry and
18 its rheological behavior was subsequently researched by rotational rheometer and viscometer.
19 It was discovered that the primary contribution to the reduction in friction during running-in is
20 better contact separation caused by the evaporation of water. However, the global behavior of
21 the solution was found to have been changed by formation of a convoluted compound and
22 probably by adsorption to contact surfaces. It causes a behavior that is more complex than that
23 predicted by common elastohydrodynamic equations, but may result in a reduction of friction
24 due to an increased separating layer.

25

26 **Keywords:** boric acid, macroscale superlubricity, elastohydrodynamic, water-based lubricants,
 27 adsorption, molecular interactions, PEG, flow properties

28

29 **Nomenclature**

Abbreviation	Explanation	Unit
Al ₂ O ₃	Sapphire (aluminum oxide)	
BK7	Borosilicate-crown glass	
BL	Boundary lubrication regime	
c ₂	Mass concentration of PEG200	(-)
CoF	Coefficient of friction	(-)
Cr	Chromium	
DLVO	Derjaguin–Landau–Verwey–Overbeek theory	
E	Young’s modulus	(GPa)
EDL	Electric double layer	
EHL	Elastohydrodynamic lubrication regime	
Eq.	Equation	
F	Load force	(N)
H ₃ BO ₃	Orthoboric acid	
h _c	Central thickness	(nm)
h _{min}	Minimal thickness	(nm)
KCl	Potassium chloride	
L _{c,ttt}	PEG200 contour length of all trans conformation	(nm)
ML	Mixed lubrication	
n	Refractive index of mixture	(-)
n ₁	Refractive index of water	(-)
n ₂	Refractive index of PEG200	(-)
N _{mol}	Number of molecule layers	(-)
p _a	Maximum (Hertz) contact pressure	(GPa)
PAGs	Polyalkylene glycols	
PEG	Polyethylene glycol	
R _F	Flory radius	(nm)
R _g	Gyration radius	(nm)
RH	Relative humidity	(%)
Si ₃ N ₄	Silicon nitride	
SiC	Silicon carbide	
Spk	Reduced peak height	(nm)
Spk ₁	Reduced peak height before running-in	(nm)
Spk ₂	Reduced peak height after running-in	(nm)
Sq	Area roughness parameter (root mean square height)	(nm)
Sq _{ball}	Sq of ball	(nm)
Sq _{disk}	Sq of disk	(nm)
Sq _{fin}	Combined roughness of the running-in ball and the disc without the running-in	(nm)
SRR	Slide-to-roll ratio	(-)
Svk	Reduced valley/pit depth	(nm)
Svk ₁	Reduced valley/pit depth before running-in	(nm)

Svk_1/Spk_1	Svk and Spk ratio before running-in	(-)
Svk_2	Reduced valley/pit depth after running-in	(nm)
Svk_2/Spk_2	Svk and Spk ratio after running-in	(-)
T-test	Statistical Student's T-test (unpaired)	
ttg	Trans-trans-gauche conformation	
ttt	Trans-trans-trans conformation	
v_b	Ball speed	(mm/s)
v_d	Disk speed	(mm/s)
wt %	Weight percent	(%)
α	Statistical level of significance	(-)
$\dot{\gamma}_T$	Theoretical/average shear rate	(10^6 s^{-1})
λ	Lubrication parameter	(-)
μ	Poisson's ratio	(-)
ρ	Density of solution	(g/cm^3)
ρ_1	Density of water	(g/cm^3)
ρ_2	Density of PEG200	(g/cm^3)
τ_T	Theoretical/average shear stress	(MPa)

30

31 1 Introduction

32 In the field of tribology, the term 'superlubricity' is used to describe a situation in which the
33 coefficient of friction (CoF) is less than 0.01 when pure sliding occurs [1, 2]. Over the past four
34 decades, numerous combinations of liquid superlubricity [3, 4] have been explored, resulting
35 in the desired reduction. Unfortunately, in practical mechanical applications such as gears,
36 bearings or hydraulic pumps, superlubricant combinations are not yet applicable [5], because
37 not all aspects of the load conditions have been resolved. For example, the high pressure at
38 start-up phase (low speed) of bearings can irreversibly damage the low friction condition.
39 Increasing the efficiency of energy use is one of the key technologies for global warming
40 mitigation [6]. It is estimated that about 20 % of CO₂ emissions could be saved through
41 increased efficiency, representing also billions of euros in costs [7].

42 To achieve such low friction under mixed (ML) or boundary (BL) lubrication regime
43 conditions, it is often concluded that running-in is necessary. Many studies assume that the
44 lubrication regime remains the same after the running-in period [5]. Consequently, the electric
45 double layer (EDL) [8–11] and hydration effects [12] are proposed as mechanisms of extremely
46 low friction. The DLVO theory, named after its authors (Derjaguin, Landau, Verwey,

47 Overbeek) [13, 14], combines part of van der Waals forces and EDL, and is also sometimes
48 used to understand the changes that occur during running-in [15]. A slight limitation of these
49 studies for mechanical tribology contacts is the specific conditions under which they are
50 conducted [5], particularly in terms of load, mean speed, materials, and ambient conditions (as
51 temperature and relative humidity [16, 17]).

52 Some published works consider the use water-based lubricants and their solutions with acids,
53 including sulfuric [10, 11], phosphoric [18, 19], boric [20, 21], and tannic acids [22], among
54 others. Additionally, hydroxides [23] and acids with salts [24, 25] can be utilized. These support
55 the adsorption of molecules and reduce the friction of the hydration layer in the dimension of
56 surface asperities. These solutions are chemically assembled as substances that enable
57 interaction with other compounds within the tribological system, thereby facilitating the
58 occurrence of intermolecular forces [26], including van der Waals [27] and in particular EDL
59 [8, 21, 28]. The van der Waals forces are mostly attractive and with hydration forces (for
60 hydrophilic materials) can cause adsorption layers with different effective viscosity of the
61 lubricant film [29]. For example, when the slip plane is present. On the other hand, in aqueous
62 solutions, EDL, as well as DLVO or solvation forces, are mostly repulsive. It can reduce the
63 apparent viscosity in the slip plane.

64 In addition to the aforementioned acids, hydroxides, or salts and water, viscous fluids such as
65 glycerol [11, 16, 30–32] or polyalkylene glycols [12, 24, 33–36] are also frequently utilized.
66 The main advantage of these fluids is their low pressure-viscosity coefficient [32, 35, 37], which
67 enables superlubricity even in highly loaded unconformal contact, especially at high speeds in
68 an elastohydrodynamic regime (EHL). Furthermore, the presence of hydroxyl groups [10, 11,
69 19, 38] renders the material suitable for interactions with glass and silicon ceramic (SiC , Si_3N_4)
70 or other non-oxidizing contact pairs capable of adsorption, facilitating the achievement of
71 interactions within the BL and ML.

72 Prior research on polyalkylene glycols (PAGs) and their solutions has demonstrated that the
73 addition of a small quantity of water can enhance the viscosity of the solution, which occurs
74 through the formation of hydrogen bonds between the water and the PAG [39]. However, the
75 pressure-viscosity coefficient decreases, resulting in a reduction in film thickness as water is
76 added [37, 39, 40]. The conventional evolution of film thickness is not observed with larger
77 amounts of water in solutions, which renders the Hamrock-Dowson [41] equations inapplicable
78 for the solution cases. Previous research conducted by our group [37] has demonstrated that
79 with low molecular weight concentrated polyethylene glycol (PEG) solutions at low speeds
80 near the transition to mixed lubrication (but still within the full EHL regime), notable deviations
81 can emerge in the lubricant film formation. These differences manifest as abrupt thickness
82 changes.

83 It has been observed that alcohols and water or their solutions have previously undergone other
84 thickness changes. In the case of dodecanol [42], it was attributed to solidification under high
85 pressure. Additionally, shear can contribute to this effect. The two polymorphs of dodecanol
86 can be formed; one of them causes solidification under high pressure, while the other causes
87 low shear lamellar fluid behavior, which supports low friction under lower load. Other research
88 has discussed the influence of glycol chains conformation and its elasticity in water solutions
89 [43]. It has been demonstrated that this can mainly influence contacts in shear conditions. Water
90 itself is then understood as capable of adsorption to hydrophilic negatively charged surface by
91 hydrated protons, i.e. hydroxonium ions, through van der Waals forces [44]. The water is then
92 densified which caused higher effective viscosity and attraction in small distances (a few
93 molecule layers).

94 The low shear of PAGs and its solutions is therefore a crucial theoretical aspect of the
95 superlubricity of water-based fluids [33, 45, 46]. Furthermore, PAGs can be adsorbed, leading
96 to the formation of hydration layers. The free water molecules between these layers then cause

97 the superlubricity state to be formed. However, not all PAGs are sufficiently charged to form
98 adsorbed layers against contact materials. Therefore, it is advisable to supplement them with
99 KCl [24], H_3BO_3 [21] or other additives and then run-in the contacts. However, not all alcohol
100 fluids contain an adequate quantity of water. Nevertheless, these fluids are hygroscopic in
101 response to relative humidity [16, 17]. Additionally, glycerol is also capable of forming water
102 molecules through tribochemical reactions [47]. Conversely, if the concentration of water
103 molecules exceeds the capacity of the fluid to absorb them in actual temperature and humidity,
104 the excess will undergo evaporation, thereby increasing the film thickness in rolling/sliding [48]
105 and also in pure sliding conditions [16, 17].

106 The investigation of rolling/sliding conditions in the superlubricity region is a relatively
107 understudied topic so far [37, 40, 47–50]. The analysis of traction curves and film thickness
108 measurements has led to the conclusion that water-based lubricants exhibit behavior that is
109 almost Newtonian [37, 40]. However, the possibility of non-Newtonian behavior [37, 50], such
110 as shear-thinning [37, 51], cannot be ruled out. As the concentration of water [37, 40, 48] or
111 temperature [47, 50] of the surrounding environment increases, the fluid behavior becomes
112 increasingly Newtonian, and the traction curve displays a gradual linear growth, i.e. ‘super-low
113 traction’ appears [49].

114 The current understanding of superlubricity in water-based lubricants is based on the formation
115 of physicochemical layers with low shear stress and the change in viscosity due to the
116 absorption of water. Additionally, a reduction in contact pressure during the running-in phase,
117 which may be accompanied by a change in roughness, is considered to be a contributory factor.
118 Nevertheless, according to these explanations, the coefficient of friction could be influenced by
119 changes in lubricant layers with sizes close to surface roughness. Observation of the film
120 thickness evolution during running-in can be essential for correct interpretation of the results
121 and their relation to known theories. The rolling/sliding conditions facilitate investigation of

122 this phenomenon, and moreover, they bring the system closer to application in non-conformal
123 contacts of real mechanical parts. Moreover, this can assist in determining the extent to which
124 the estimated factors contributing to the reduction in the CoF ultimately influence its final value.
125 This paper is concerned with the running-in of polyethylene glycol, water, and boric acid,
126 examining their properties both before and after the test. The objective is to elucidate the actual
127 film thickness at the contact interface and, consequently, the prevailing lubrication regimes in
128 the context of the running-in changes. It can be supported by observations of the
129 interrelationships between the film thickness and the estimated weak interactions at the contact
130 point. Additionally, this study contributes to the existing knowledge of abrupt changes [37] in
131 polyethylene glycol (PEG) solutions in film thickness.

132 **2 Materials and methods**

133 Experiments were performed in a laboratory setting at a temperature of 24.5 ± 1.5 °C, with a
134 relative humidity approximately 30-40 % RH.

135 **2.1 Lubricants and contact materials**

136 The PEG with a molecular weight of 200 g/mol, further labeled as PEG200 (obtained from
137 Sigma-Aldrich, Inc., Chemical Abstract Service (CAS) No. 25322-68-3), distilled water, and
138 boric acid (H_3BO_3 , obtained from Ing. Petr Švec - PENTA s.r.o, CAS No. 10043-35-3). The
139 initial mixture was identical to that described in the reference article [21] and consisted of 66.7
140 wt % water, 31.7 wt % PEG200, and 1.6 wt % H_3BO_3 . This mixture was labeled as B-
141 PEG200(aq). In the second mixture, designated as PEG200(aq), the acid was omitted, resulting
142 in a solution comprising 67.78 wt % water and 32.22 wt % PEG200. The compositions of both
143 mixtures are presented in Table 1. To prevent subsequent degradation [52] of the polymer in
144 solution and to reach equilibrium [53], the samples were prepared more than 30 days in
145 advance. During the storage period, the samples were maintained at a temperature consistent
146 with that of a laboratory setting environment.

147 **Table 1** Composition of the investigated solutions

	Water (wt %)	PEG200 (wt %)	H ₃ BO ₃ (wt %)
B-PEG200(aq)	66.70	31.70	1.60
PEG200(aq)	67.78	32.22	0.00

148

149 In all tests, a low roughness silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) ball with a radius of 12.7 nm was used. The
 150 opposing contact material was either optical glass (BK7) or sapphire (Al₂O₃). Properties of
 151 these contact materials are listed in Table 2. The surfaces were examined using an optical
 152 profilometer (Contour GT-X8, Bruker, USA). The utilization of sapphire disk was used to avoid
 153 the chemical influence of worn silicon particles, which could potentially migrate from the glass
 154 into the lubricant during the running-in period [54]. Its transition to silica gel then can affect
 155 adsorption layers and also viscosity change. A glass disk with a chromium layer may serve a
 156 comparable function and was used to measure the thickness of the lubricant layer. However,
 157 the running-in tests may result in abrasion of the Cr layer, rendering it unsuitable for use in
 158 these tests.

159 **Table 2** Properties of contact materials used and loads applied during tests

Materials (ball/disk)	Sq (nm)	E (GPa)	μ	F (N)	p _a (GPa)
Si₃N₄/glass BK7	22.6/1.1	310/81	0.25/0.206	30 ; 35; 60	0.547 ; 0.575; 0.689
Si₃N₄/Al₂O₃	22.6/1.0	310/435	0.25/0.27	35	1.165

160

161 2.2 Tribometer and lubricant delivery

162 Tribological measurements were conducted using an optical ball-on-disk tribometer (Brno University
 163 of Technology, Czech Republic), which provided the value of the friction coefficient and lubricating
 164 film thickness. The coefficient of friction was recalculated from the value of the torque sensor, which
 165 exhibited a nonlinearity error of 0.0007 CoF at a load of 30 N. The ball is mounted on a shaft supported

166 by ball bearings, the effect of which was subtracted in the calibration of the individual measurements
 167 (for a ball speed of 100 mm/s and a load of 30 N, the calibration value is approximately CoF 0.0027).
 168 The CoF values for SRR (see Eq. (1)) from -0.5 to 0.5 were measured and the value of the loss torque
 169 at SRR = 0 % (pure rolling) was subtracted from all measured values to maintain the same conversion
 170 to CoF.

$$171 \quad SRR = \frac{2 \cdot (v_b - v_d)}{(v_b + v_d)} \quad 173 \quad (1)$$

172
 174 The lubricant was applied to the contact mainly by syringe, as shown in Fig. 1. The possibility
 175 of tribochemical interactions is reduced and the running-in time is shortened [21] compared to
 176 that provided by immersion lubrication due to the volume of the solution. It is presumed that
 177 the changed lubricant could be washed out by the fresh lubricant from the reservoir or
 178 contaminated by previous residual lubricant. Furthermore, if the syringe was not utilized, the
 179 evolution of friction and the lubricating film could not have been observed. In the running-in
 180 and time tests (see Table 3), the lubricant was applied exclusively during the initial minute. The
 181 measurement was conducted without interruption, with the lubricant sample adhered to the
 182 contact surfaces.

183
 184 **Fig. 1** Lubricant delivery to contact in a ball-on disk tribometer

185 The two tests, namely the running-in and time tests, were conducted with a mean speed of 100
 186 mm/s. In the event that shear stress (SRR) was present, the glass was uncoated, and the test was
 187 named as "running-in". In the event that the SRR was 0 %, the chromium-coated disk was
 188 utilized, and the test was named as "time." The standard load in these tests was 30 N, and the

189 duration was 3.5 hours, as indicated in Table 3. In the Stribeck test, the mean velocity was
190 initially 1,000 mm/s and then gradually decreased to 0.1 mm/s, after which it was accelerated
191 again to reach the final velocity of 1,000 mm/s.

192 **Table 3** Tests performed and their conditions (standard load indicated)

	time (h)	SRR (%)	F (N)	p_a (GPa)	Cr layer
running-in test	3.5	0.5	30	0.547	No
time test	3.5	0	30	0.547	Yes
Stribeck test	-	0.5	30	0.547	Yes/No

193
194 Following the completion of the running-in tests, the film thickness of the solution could be
195 determined through the use of interferometric colorimetry, employing a glass disk with a
196 chromium layer. The lubricant was transferred from the disk lacking chromium to the other disk
197 with chromium, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Two transfer steps were conducted. Initially,
198 approximately half of the run-in solution was imprinted, and then the remaining half was
199 manually transferred using a stainless-steel spatula to the anticipated contact path. The solution
200 volume was less than that of the run-in path, and when high speeds were applied, starvation
201 could occur. However, these results were not included in the subsequent analysis.

202

203 **Fig. 2** Method of transferring lubricant after running-in from a disk without a chromium layer

204 to the other with it

205

206 2.3 Measure physical/chemical changes in lubricants after testing

207 The quantity of individual components in the solution was prepared with the aid of a precision

208 balance (KERN ABJ 320-4NM, Balingen, Germany), which is capable of reading to 0.1 mg.

209 Subsequently, the instrument was utilized to assess the water evaporation of the lubricant under

210 investigation (changes in density). In this instance, capillaries of known mass and defined

211 volume (20 μ l) were employed. Following the testing phase, the lubricant was drawn into the

212 capillary and weighed. The calculated density can then be compared with that of other samples

213 of PEG solution. This procedure is more time-consuming; thus, a refractive index measurement

214 by an Abbe refractometer can also be used to detect alterations in the mixture. The measured

215 values can be interpreted as changes in density, provided that sufficient solutions are available,

216 using the Lorentz-Lorentz relationship for mixtures [55].

$$\rho = \frac{\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2}}{\frac{1 - c_2}{\rho_1} \cdot \left(\frac{n_1^2 - 1}{n_1^2 + 2}\right) + \frac{c_2}{\rho_2} \cdot \left(\frac{n_2^2 - 1}{n_2^2 + 2}\right)} \quad (2)$$

218

221 In this calculation, see Eq. (2), boric acid and its effect are neglected. In this equation, n
 222 represents the measured refractive index of the mixture, n_1 denotes the refractive index of
 223 water, n_2 denotes the refractive index of PEG200, ρ_1 is the density of water, ρ_2 is the density
 224 of PEG200, and c_2 signifies the mass concentration of PEG200 in the mixture.

225 The Höppler viscometer (AMVn Automated Micro Viscometer, Anton Paar, Graz, Austria),
 226 densitometer (DMA 4500, Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) and rotational rheometer (Discovery HR-
 227 2, TA Instruments, New Castle, USA) were employed to analyze the rheological behavior of
 228 lubrication samples. Pure PEG200 and its solutions were employed for comparison with B-
 229 PEG200(aq) both before and after the running-in tests. The sufficient amount of solution after
 230 the running-in was achieved by collecting the lubricant from the disk after several tests (ranging
 231 from 3 to 14), resulting in an average yield of 0.2 to 1.1 ml. A greater quantity of solution was
 232 employed for the viscometer, whereas a lower quantity was utilized for the rheometer, which
 233 employed a parallel plate configuration.

234 Rheometry measurement consisted of conditioning step, in which the sample was let to temper,
 235 and flow sweep itself. Dynamic viscosity was measured between 10 and 1,000 s^{-1} with six
 236 points per decade. These tests were conducted in duplicates always with freshly loaded sample.
 237 For the viscometry measurement, glass capillary and ball were used. Measuring angle was 60°
 238 and final viscosity value was evaluated as average of four repetitions. All measuring parameters
 239 are listed in summarizing Table 4.

240

241 **Table 4** Viscometer and rheometer settings and properties

Rheometer	Viscometer
-----------	------------

<i>Conditioning step</i>			
Temperature	25 °C		25 °C
Time	2 min		2 min
Measuring gap	200 µm		
<i>Measuring step</i>			
Temperature	25 °C		25 °C
Geometry serial number	109411	Capillary serial number	13190613
Geometry diameter	8 mm	Capillary diameter	1.6 mm
Shear rate	10 to 1,000 s ⁻¹	Ball diameter	1.5 mm
Points per decade	6	Measuring angle	60°
Measuring gap	200 µm	Number of repetitions	4

242

243 A further observation was made concerning the liquid/solid interface. A Manta G-146B ASG
 244 monochrome camera (Allied Vision, Stadtroda, Germany) with a telecentric lens (1X, 65mm
 245 WD CompactTL, Edmund Optics, Barrington, USA) was utilized to record the droplet image.
 246 Subsequently, the contact angle was evaluated using the DropSnake [56] plugin in the ImageJ
 247 [57] software, which is used for scientific image analysis. For clarity, the images used later in
 248 this work were modified in Inkscape.

249 The results of film thickness and coefficient of friction can be made more useful by
 250 recalculation to (theoretical) shear stress and (theoretical) shear rate, respectively, in accordance
 251 with the following equations:

$$252 \quad \dot{\gamma}_T = \frac{v_b - v_d}{0.7 \cdot h_c} \quad 254 \quad (3)$$

253

$$255 \quad \tau_T = CoF \cdot \frac{2}{3} \cdot p_a \quad 256 \quad (4)$$

257

258 Subsequently, the outcomes may be compared with the flow curves derived from the rheometric
 259 measurements. In Eq. (3) of the shear rate, the coefficient 0.7 is employed as a ratio between

260 the minimal and central (h_c) film thickness. In Eq. (4) of the shear stress, the value of 2/3 is
261 utilized to recalculate the mean contact pressure from the maximum (Hertz) contact pressure.

262

263 3 Results and discussion

264 The progress of the running-in test of Si₃N₄ and glass in this research (Fig. 3) is analogous to
265 that observed by Ge et al. [21] under comparable conditions. The primary distinction between
266 the tests is the partial rolling and the alteration in the dimensions of the contact area at the outset
267 of the running-in phase. This may be the reason for the lower initial coefficient of friction (CoF)
268 and its less pronounced reduction, but to a lower value (CoF = 0.003). Furthermore, the quantity
269 of lubricant and the method of its application to the contact surface (injection – see Fig. 1)
270 differ. The longer running-in time can be attributed to the larger radius of the contact path and
271 thus higher volume of solution. The excess amount of injected lubricant flowed into the
272 equipment reservoir and did not influence the subsequent process. Despite the differences, the
273 steady state following the running-in period persists for approximately six hours, with the
274 potential for an even longer duration. It can therefore be assumed that the transformation of the
275 lubricant system corresponds to those previously described [20, 21].

276

277 **Fig. 3** Typical running-in with steady-state CoF value

278

279 **3.1 Running-in thickness and topography observation**

280 Subsequently, the analysis of running-in was extended for an evaluation of film thickness in
281 pure rolling. The results were compared with the coefficient of friction in conditions of 50 %
282 SRR (Fig. 4). It was observed that the lubrication regime had transitioned from a severe mixed
283 lubrication ($\lambda < 1$), characterized by frequent contact between asperities of the surfaces, to a
284 mixed lubrication with only occasional contact between asperities ($\lambda \approx 1$). This classification is
285 based on the lubrication parameter (Eq. (5)) and its description, as mentioned by Vergne [49].
286 When the λ is approximately equal to 1, the viscosity of the lubricant is probably higher, but
287 still very low. The pure rolling friction decreases, while the film thickness exhibits a slight
288 increase. The boundary part of friction is almost missing due to the absence of asperities
289 interactions. When rolling/sliding conditions are established, the CoF remains largely
290 unchanged. It is improbable that slight increases in viscosity and thickness could succeed in
291 overcoming the considerable impact of occasional contact between uneven surfaces. In the third
292 region ($\lambda \approx 2.5$), a notable increase in thickness, i.e. viscosity, is observed. In the case of pure
293 rolling, this signifies a return to the original friction values, which are influenced by higher
294 viscosity and a reduction in the number of contacts between asperities. In rolling/sliding,
295 however, the CoF decreases significantly, which can probably be attributed mainly to the
296 greater surface separation and the transition to the full EHL regime.

297 Although the theoretical onset of this event ($\lambda = 3$ [49]) is valid for a Gaussian surface and a
298 certain percentage/probability of contacts, optical observation of the Si_3N_4 surface irregularities
299 on the sphere indicates that the predominant features are depressions/pits, which may influence
300 the thickness [58, 59]. The reduced valley/pit depth (Svk) is higher than the reduced peak height
301 (Spk) both before (Svk_1/Spk_1) and after running-in (Svk_2/Spk_2), see Table 5 for complete
302 information. The ceramic ball exhibited a statistically significant (T-test, $\alpha = 0.05$) decrease in
303 both parameters over the course of the running-in period. In contrast, both disks demonstrated

304 an increase in these parameters. The Svk/Spk ratio underwent a statistically significant (T-test,
 305 $\alpha = 0.05$) change for both the glass disk and the ceramic ball, favoring the valley. The
 306 combination of contact materials therefore results in a high number of pits on the surfaces,
 307 which creates an imbalanced ratio of Svk and Spk . Consequently, the absence of protrusions in
 308 the transition region precludes the application of the λ parameter as a determinant in accurate
 309 regime classification [60]. On the other hand, it is probably still suitable for preliminary analysis.
 310 Although the chemical/physical interactions could also play a role [34, 44, 61, 62].

$$311 \quad \lambda = \frac{h_{min}}{\sqrt{Sq_{ball}^2 + Sq_{disk}^2}} \quad 312 \quad (5)$$

313 where h_{min} represents the minimum film thickness and the denominator is the combined
 314 roughness after running-in (Sq_{fin}).

315 **Table 5** Means of ratios of the reduced valley depth and the reduced peak height before
 316 (1) and after (2) the running-in

	Svk_1/Spk_1	Svk_2/Spk_2
Ball (Si₃N₄)	2.84 ± 0.08	3.61 ± 0.35
Disk (BK7 glass)	1.16 ± 0.15	2.06 ± 0.22
Disk (Al₂O₃)	0.75 ± 0.27	0.64 ± 0.09
Si₃N₄ + BK7 glass	3.06 ± 0.17	4.16 ± 0.41
Si₃N₄ + Al₂O₃	2.93 ± 0.28	3.67 ± 0.36

317

318

319

320 **Fig. 4** Observation of the coefficient of friction (SRR 0% and 50 %) and film thickness (SRR
 321 0 %) evolution during running-in

322 A slight alteration was observed in the roughness of the contact surfaces, particularly in the
 323 case of glass, where the surface roughness increased to $13.9 \pm 2.1 \text{ nm Sq}$. The alterations in the
 324 ball's trajectory were initially indistinguishable (not statistically significant); however,
 325 following 15 additional runs, the path could be accurately gauged, yielding a value of 9.6 ± 0.6
 326 nm Sq . This represents a decline of approximately 50 % in comparison to the value documented
 327 in Table 2. Therefore, the mean value of the combined roughness of both surfaces changed from
 328 22.7 to 16.9 nm Sq , which is within the combined standard deviation range. The same ball was
 329 used throughout all further tests, and the roughness remained practically unchanged.
 330 Consequently, for the evaluation of time tests (Table 3) or tests after imprinting (Fig. 2), when
 331 the disk topography remained unchanged, the combined roughness (BK7/Si₃N₄) was taken as
 332 9.7 $\text{nm} (Sq_{\text{fin}})$. This value was also utilized to determine the lubrication parameter according
 333 to Eq. (5) for an initial estimation of the lubrication regime, as presented in Fig. 4.

334 In the case of the Al_2O_3 surface (data available in Zenodo repository), the friction exhibited a
335 decrease during the initial hour, followed by a significant increase. By the 90th minute, the CoF
336 value had already exceeded 0.01. At the 190th minute, the highest value was recorded (0.018),
337 and at the 220th minute, when the experiment was terminated, a slight decrease was observed
338 (0.017). The combined roughness ($\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) increased from 22.6 to 23.6 nm Sq, which
339 probably strongly influenced the CoF progress. The number of peaks also increased, which
340 could affect the final CoF because the area of direct contact had increased [60]. The higher
341 contact pressure (smaller contact area) than in the case of the glass disk and the film viscosity
342 change could also be significant factors in the CoF evolution.

343 **3.2 Rheology PEG200 solutions changes during the running-in**

344 The change in apparent viscosity as a function of shear rate observed during the course of the
345 experiments was subsequently investigated as part of the post-testing analysis. The evaluation
346 of Höppler viscometer data was performed by utilizing the density values. However, given that
347 only approximately 60 μl of sample could be collected following the running-in test, the density
348 of the sample was initially measured and evaluated using only capillaries. The densitometer
349 was not employed in this characterization due to the insufficient amount of the sample. The
350 remaining samples that did not pass the running-in test were measured both using
351 a densitometer (see Fig. 5) and by capillary (see Fig. 6). In addition, data from refractive index
352 measurements and recalculation according to Eq. (2) were employed. It can be established that
353 there was a significant increase in density after the running-in, which correlates with 83.9 ± 5.9
354 % of PEG200 in the solution (neglecting H_3BO_3) according to Fig. 6. The high standard
355 deviation can be attributed to two factors: firstly, the considerable range of relative humidity
356 and temperature under which the tests were conducted; and secondly, the relatively low number
357 of capillary tests. Based on the viscometer data, the amount varies only in tenths of a percent,
358 which is sufficiently covered by the standard deviation. Therefore, it can be concluded that

359 there is a relatively high evaporation of water (from 66.7 % to about 20 wt %) during the
 360 running-in period. It suggests that the remaining water is tightly bound within the solution [33,
 361 45]. This phenomenon may be attributed to the attachment of water molecules to the hydroxyl
 362 groups present in the helical structure of PEG [43, 63, 64]. This hypothesis is supported by
 363 previous studies that have observed the presence of both trans and gauche conformations in
 364 PEG chains, as well as in double PEG400 structures [65]. Although chemical changes in the
 365 composition of the solutions may occur during the running-in period, such as degradation of
 366 PEG [66, 67] – similar to glycerol [38, 47], PEGylation [52, 68], or gelation without borate
 367 necessity [55, 65, 69] or with it [70], these are not included in the calculation of the change in
 368 water content. However, it can be reasonably assumed that the calculated change in water
 369 content is very close to the actual amount, given the known relationship between relative
 370 humidity and the amount of glycerol in solutions [16, 71].

371
 372 **Fig. 5** Effect of running-in on density and dynamic viscosity of solutions compared to pure
 373 PEG200

374

375 **Fig. 6** Density dependence on the amount of PEG200 (capillary test and refractive index)

376 The density was utilized to evaluation the dynamic viscosity, as also shown in Fig. 5. It can be
 377 stated that boric acid has a significant effect (T-test, $\alpha = 0.05$) on the magnitude of dynamic
 378 viscosity. However, more interesting is the observation that the viscosity of B-PEG200(aq) after
 379 the running-in period is about 27.6 times greater than that of the solution prior to the abrupt
 380 change illustrated in Fig. 4. Furthermore, it is approx. 1.8 times larger than the dynamic
 381 viscosity of pure PEG200. The results for PEG200 are in alignment with the trends of density
 382 and viscosity identified by Sequeira et al. [72] at atmospheric pressure. Hofmann et al. [48]
 383 described how the addition of water determines the density, viscosity and film thickness.
 384 According to the results in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 the observed changes could not be fully explained
 385 by the amount of water alone. Conversely, in the case of PEG solutions without running-in,
 386 these principles appear to be applicable. It is also important to note that, despite the fact that the
 387 mixtures in this study are almost Newtonian, they exhibit a shear-thickening behavior (see Fig.
 388 7). This may account for the reduced applicability of the viscosity measurements taken from
 389 Höppler viscometer. This effect can be observed most strongly in the boric acid mixture.

390

391 **Fig. 7** Effect of water amount and running-in on dynamic viscosity and flow sweep

392 One explanation for these changes is that the combination of shear stress and high pressure can
 393 cause the chemical decomposition of polyhydric (PEG) molecules [38], resulting in the
 394 formation of strongly polar carboxylic acids or reactive aldehydes and water. It is therefore
 395 easily to assume that these products can form more complete molecule structures based on the
 396 principles of PEGylation [52, 68] or gelation [69] (spread-gel [65]). However, the gel transition
 397 point was not approved by rheological measurements, even though it could be presumed
 398 according to the quantity of water in solution [65, 69]. Consequently, as only a limited volume
 399 of fluid can be examined following the running-in periods, the probability of gelation is
 400 reduced, however, not completely eliminated.

401 A comparable system for the production of a higher viscosity lubricant could be generated from
 402 the decay of PEG to free radicals [66] caused by pressure and stress and subsequent synthesis
 403 reaction (e.g. PEGylation or gelation). It should also be noted that even if only rolling is
 404 between the contact bodies, the hydrodynamic stress [73] with contact pressure can contribute
 405 to macromolecule degradation [67, 74], as has been previously reported . It is also important to
 406 consider that the formation of complex molecules can be influenced by the effect of
 407 confinement [75]. This could also be a contributing factor to the gelation process.

408 The majority of research conducted on confined liquids focuses on the known thickness of the
 409 liquid [44, 75, 76]. The distance between the surfaces of the liquid and the surrounding
 410 environment has been identified as a crucial factor influencing the rheological behavior of the

411 liquid. In this instance, the perspective adopted is reversed, with the thickness representing the
412 variable. Therefore, it cannot be employed in equation of a parameter of degree of confinement
413 [75] or in other equation expressing the size of polymers and its relationship to the formation
414 of confined liquid layers [76]. Nevertheless, the gyration radius (R_g), Flory radius (R_F) or
415 contour length may prove to be a valuable parameter for elucidating the underlying mechanisms
416 of lubrication system behavior during abrupt changes [29, 43, 76, 77]. The investigated
417 solutions of PEG200 have a lower molar mass than that of the previously studied [75], therefore
418 the calculation of R_g (4.72 nm) from the [78] is not applicable. According to Israelachvili [29],
419 the sizes of bonds and atoms give a smaller value than even the monomer contour length (3.59
420 Å – own calculation). It seems likely that this size is also not entirely accurate, in that it neglects
421 to consider the attraction forces and the type of conformation present in the PEG monomer [43].
422 According to this, the contour length of the "all trans" (ttt) conformation is 3.58 Å [43], which
423 equates to 1.48 nm for PEG200. The contour length of the "trans-trans-gauche" (ttg)
424 conformation is 2.8 Å [43], which equates to 1.16 nm for PEG200.

425 These values can be used to divide the film thickness in order to approximate the number of
426 molecules situated between the asperities of the surfaces in question. At the initial stage of the
427 running-in process (Fig. 4), the asperities are in direct contact, with no molecular separation
428 between the central regions of the contact bodies. This indicates that the molecules do not
429 separate the surfaces, but rather occupy the spaces between the asperities. Following the abrupt
430 change in central film thickness, the number of molecules increases to approximately 28.2. In
431 the area of minimum film thickness, the number can be calculated to be 8.6 (after running-in).
432 These principles can be linked to computer simulations by Young-Hwa Kim in Israelachvili et
433 al. [29], where the density of molecules can increase with a decrease in the amount of water
434 (poorer solvents) and brush adsorption layers can occur. These calculations are also discussed
435 in Section 3.4.

436 **3.3 Interface of PEG200 solutions and contact bodies**

437 In the absence of a compound formation, such as a gel or a complex (e.g. a cluster), which
438 would otherwise cause the changes illustrated in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it is useful to ascertain
439 whether there is a possibility of lubricant adsorption on the contact surfaces. Such an occurrence
440 could potentially impact the viscosity of the liquid in contact [79, 80]. Subsequently, the
441 increasing of viscosity at a distance of tens of nanometers may be affected by adsorption. The
442 influence of viscosity can also occur with metal surfaces or coatings [81], and not only with
443 glass or Al₂O₃ [82]. However, it should be noted that more hydrophilic surfaces are more
444 suitable for adsorption [81]. It can be inferred that the rheometer evaluation should remain
445 unaffected, but the film thickness may be influenced. For this reason, the wetting angle was
446 determined inside and outside of the run-in path of the glass surface (see Fig. 8), where only
447 the disk without the Cr layer was used. The values are notably different, and it can be observed
448 that the wetting angle is smaller after the run-in period. This may also be attributed to the
449 alteration in surface roughness [83]. However, it was not optically observable for some
450 measurements and was only located under small part of droplet. To mitigate the impact of
451 roughness, measurements were obtained within a minute of the droplet's application to the
452 surface.

453

454 **Fig. 8** Contact angles inside and outside the run-in path on the glass disk

455 The influence of cohesion on the wetting angle was also considered. Consequently, a lubricant
 456 sample (after the running-in test) was initially applied to the intact surface area. The areas
 457 designated for future droplet application were wiped with a pulp cloth. The droplets were
 458 applied via capillary action, and the wetting angles were subsequently measured. It was found
 459 that the wetting angle inside the path was 12.0 ± 0.3 after the running-in period, while outside
 460 the path it was 25.3 ± 6.9 . The results indicate that the hydrophilicity of the solid/liquid
 461 interface, as well as the adsorption of the polymer can be presumed [81, 84]. The elevated
 462 degree of variability outside the path is likely attributable to the small number of tests conducted
 463 and the time differences between the sample application and the measurement period. The
 464 larger the delay, the greater the adsorption, and thus the smaller the contact angle. In order to
 465 eliminate the effect of cohesion, the surface was also cleaned with acetone and then measured;
 466 however, the repeatability of the results deteriorated. Nevertheless, slight changes between the

467 wetting angle after running-in (21.4 ± 5.2) and outside the path (30.6 ± 9.0) could still be
468 observed.

469 It is established that correlation exists between the contact angle and replenishment [85]. As
470 well, the quantity of lubricant can influence the shape of the flow area and the film thickness
471 [86, 87]. Some of these changes were detected when the mean speed was increased. The
472 subsequent observation was the monitoring of the contact area following the time test (SRR =
473 0 %, B-PEG200(aq)) using a microscope (for interferometric evaluation of film thickness) and
474 concurrently by visual and photographic means in order to ascertain whether it could affect
475 thickness during the Stribeck test. As depicted in Fig. 9, the flow area assumes a butterfly shape
476 [85] during acceleration to approximately 170 mm/s. The replenishment was observed to be as
477 effective as required to prevent starvation, even when the amount of lubricant was relatively
478 low and the thickness was increasing. This suggests that the meniscus distance was much higher
479 than the Hertzian radius [85, 86]. Subsequently, speed was decreased, which did not usually
480 result in the enclosure of the flow shape. The reduction in the minimal film thickness was
481 unlikely to be caused by a change in the flow shape or lubricant amount, as the progress of the
482 lubrication layer was similar when the speed was increased or decreased. This suggests that the
483 flow shape changes did not affect the lubrication layer. Further increases in the film thickness
484 were then observed when the mean speed was above 400 mm/s. Moreover, slight differences in
485 the lubricant amount resulted in the transition from an enclosed to a butterfly flow shape at
486 varying speeds, but this had no effect on the behavior of the film thickness.

487

488 **Fig. 9** Shape of fluid flow in the contact area depending on thickness/velocity

489 3.4 Effect of mean speed on film thickness evolution

490 The wetting angle may be influenced by surface tension, with alterations observable in the
 491 friction and spreading [88, 89] and potentially linked to the film thickness [90]. In our previous
 492 research [37], the abrupt thickness changes were observed. These changes are analogous to
 493 those observed in solutions with or without boric acid, as illustrated in Fig. 10. It is important
 494 to note that the thickness changes are less abrupt than those observed in the absence of running-
 495 in. These findings correspond approximately to the amount of water in the solution, as
 496 determined by density measurement. The tests conducted with boric acid in the solutions
 497 demonstrated a higher central thickness than those conducted without it. The elevated viscosity
 498 and density observed in Fig. 5 are presumed to be the primary factors contributing to the
 499 observed increase in film thickness after the running-in. Furthermore, pure rolling supports and
 500 facilitates the formation of the film. It is evident there is an abrupt change at 75 mm/s (yellow
 501 dots), followed by another change at approximately 350 mm/s (almost 40 %). When the SRR
 502 was 50 % (green dots), these changes were less evident, yet still discernible. These results
 503 provide slight support for the idea of PEG chain adsorption, as previously presented in this
 504 discussion (Section 3.3) and in the literature [80–82, 84]. At thicknesses below 50 nm,
 505 interactions such as van der Waals forces, EDL, and hydration ought to be considered at the
 506 macroscale [29, 79]. The formation of adsorption layers can be influenced below this value. In
 507 addition to carboxylic acids or reactive aldehydes (discussed in Section 3.2), PEG chains ending

508 in methyl ethers can also be formed during the running-in process [63]. It can be presumed that
 509 the initiated chains are then strongly adsorbed (attracted) to the glass or Si₃N₄ surface than to
 510 the Cr layer. If correct, the initial layer could even be higher and strongly interacts with other
 511 molecules, as could be assumed for PEG chains [63] (cf. Section 15.3 and 16.3). Some
 512 interactions could also be hypothesized for the Cr layer, as a metal [81]. One potential
 513 justification for this is that complexes may be formed by metal binding [63] (chromium or
 514 boron) to PEG200, which could also be weakly attracted.

515
 516 **Fig. 10** Central film thickness changes depending on mean speed and solution composition

517 Even the boron, a metalloid, has the capacity to form gels [70]. The boric acid may be the
 518 component of the solution that can facilitate the formation of a more robust (spread) gel than
 519 that of a PEG200 water solution [65]. The complicated structures of PEG, as discussed in
 520 Section 3.2, are likely the reason for the observed thickness changes above 50 nm. It seems
 521 probable that the PEG transformation through the running-in process is incomplete. This
 522 suggests that PEG may also be present in pure form, but swollen by the presence of water and
 523 cis or gauche conformation [43, 63, 91]. The transition behavior of two phases [63] can be
 524 observed (Fig. 10). Two forms of solution can be identified: one composed of PEG200 and

525 bonded water, and the other composed of newly formed, more complex molecules and bonded
526 water. This is supported by the differing speeds of thickness change observed in accelerating
527 and decelerating, which can be described as the hysteresis of the bulk solution system. The
528 unaged solution (red dots) exhibited the most pronounced hysteresis.

529 It is also possible that the conformation transformation is the cause of the initial thickness
530 change. If only a common PEG200 hydrodynamic radius (0.430 nm [91]) is considered, it
531 implies a shift from 66.7 layers (38.4 nm) to 92.8 layers (49.6 nm) for B-PEG200(aq) – yellow
532 dots. Such a result would appear to be implausible. However, the temperature in the contact can
533 also be an important factor in this case and can cause changes in the radius size, similar to some
534 microgels [92]. However, if the process of adsorption is considered, the chains are expected to
535 be stretched. In the case of the ttg conformation (see end of Section 3.2), a thickness of 38.4 nm
536 corresponds to 25.0 molecular layers, according to Eq. (6). For the tt conformation and a
537 thickness of 49.6 nm, the corresponding value is 27.0 layers (half at one surface). The similarity
538 in value indicates that the change of conformation may be considered. Although it is
539 challenging to accept, it is probable that weak interactions can withstand hydrodynamic shear
540 and Hertzian pressure, resulting in the elongation of molecules until collapse and a consequent
541 shift in film thickness. It should be noted, however, that this evaluation is based on the central
542 film thickness and that the contact area is more complex, including thinner thickness areas. Fig.
543 11 illustrates that the minimal thickness exhibits abrupt changes of the same magnitude as the
544 central thickness. Additionally, it depicts the number of layers in contact during the tests (and
545 thickness changes) and the regimes, according to the theory of parameter λ [49], in which film
546 transformation could be observed.

547

$$548 \quad N_{mol} = \frac{h_c - Sq_{fin}}{L_{c_ttt}} \quad 549 \quad (6)$$

550 where the L_{c_ttt} is contour length of all trans conformation.

551
 552 **Fig. 11** Influence of the theoretical number of molecules in the central contact area on the
 553 formation of the lubrication layer and its changes after the time test, B-PEG200(aq)
 554 The ageing of the solution is probably also a relevant factor, given the noticeable differences
 555 between the solution (PEG200(aq)) prepared a month before the test and the solution prepared
 556 on the same day (denoted as newPEG200(aq) in Fig. 10). Furthermore, these findings lend
 557 support to the claim that the solutions exhibit two distinct phases. It is evident that the ageing
 558 of the solution is unimportant with regard to the detection of transition that occurs in both cases,
 559 whereby the system is transferred into the bulk EHL. The mean thickness exhibits a step change
 560 at a comparable point with the slip during the running-in, as without the running-in [37], but
 561 with the distinction that the lubricant exhibits a larger reduction (newPEG200(aq)) or addition
 562 (PEG200(aq)) in thickness. It can also be assumed that the ageing and running-in process affects
 563 not only the viscosity of the resulting mixture, but also the coefficient of friction in the presence
 564 as well as in the absence of boron. In the case of a new mixture, water evaporation does occur
 565 and the resulting behavior of the fluid corresponds closer to that of a mixture of the similar
 566 density without running-in [37], as is also the case according to [48]. The thickness of possibly

567 adsorbed lubricant before the abrupt change is in the case of nePEG200(aq) lower than of the
568 bulk trend, which is probably due to the fact that more complex stable molecules have not
569 formed in the lubricant. The beneficial outcome of the solution aging can be understood as
570 stabilization and aggregation process leading to better contact separation in the ML.

571 With regard to the sapphire disk, the evolution of the 2D profile thickness subsequent to the
572 running-in period exhibited a comparable trend to that observed in the glass disk (data available
573 in Zenodo repository). The difference was observed in the fact that it exhibited the highest
574 lubricant film thickness in all the measurements. The transition regions of the thickness were
575 recorded, but were less noticeable. This may be attributed to the higher viscosity of the mixture
576 (not measured) that is formed during the running-in process, which could be the result of the
577 reaction between boric acid and the material [93]. An additional potential explanation is the
578 adsorption of the thicker layer onto the contact bodies [82]. As in the other cases, the thicknesses
579 did not exceed the values given by pure PEG200 above 200 mm/s. Below this speed, the pure
580 liquid exhibits a step reduction in the lubrication layer. Consequently, B-PEG200(aq) can
581 achieve a higher lubrication layer at lower velocities in both the glass and Al₂O₃ disk cases.

582 **3.5 Elastohydrodynamic and PEG200 solutions behavior**

583 The film thickness (SRR = 0 %) and coefficient of friction (SRR = 0.5 %) were measured after
584 the imprinting and can be recalculated according to Eq. (3) and Eq. (4), as is illustrated in Fig.
585 12. The three dotted lines represent the mean speed, with the coefficient of friction (CoF) below
586 zero following calibration. These values are the average of two tests. It seems probable that this
587 is a consequence of the inherent errors of the device. The lowest displayed average shear stress
588 is recalculated from 0.00022 CoF. The first dotted line can be attributed to the highest shear
589 rate at which separation in the center of contact began to occur. The remaining two can be
590 assigned together with the lowest shear stress. This is in accordance with the data illustrated in
591 Fig. 11, where it corresponds to the initial change in the central film thickness.

592 More tests were carried out between the imprinting and the thickness measurement, so the result
593 (Fig. 12) corresponds more to the thicknesses after the time test. As a consequence, the initial
594 central film thickness change can be successfully identified within the range of 40 to 75 mm/s.
595 At around 300 mm/s there is a further change in the slope of the shear rate (second central
596 thickness change). Nevertheless, the Hamrock-Dowson [41] equations could only be used after
597 the complete separation of the contacts by the bulk liquid, probably of higher viscosity. That is,
598 after the 700 mm/s when the second minimum film thickness change occurred (Fig. 11). And it
599 can also be seen that the average shear stress does not increase after that. This could be caused
600 by thermal effects [94] or by the shear thickening behavior of the slightly non-Newtonian liquid
601 as presented in Section 3.2 and in Fig. 7. The rheological behavior of the solutions examined in
602 this study is complex and can be estimated from the data presented in Fig. 12.

603 As previously demonstrated by Luo et al. [95, 96] for lubricants where molecular interaction
604 can influence EHL behavior, the established speed index (0.67) for central film thickness
605 prediction [41] can be applied only after the last thickness alteration. The pressure-viscosity
606 coefficient (7.84 GPa^{-1} , $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and viscosity (47.3 mPas , $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), which is in accordance with
607 the findings of [97, 98], can be used for pure PEG200 [37] in this context. It is important to
608 note that these values are influenced by the amount of water, and thus require modification
609 according to the specific conditions, such as relative humidity [16]. Furthermore, the Hamrock-
610 Dowson formulas [41] may be utilized for the purpose of retrospective pressure-viscosity
611 estimation from central film thickness. Upon loading the contact by 30 N, the estimated value
612 was 3.6 GPa^{-1} . However, for 11 N, the estimated value was 4.1 GPa^{-1} , and for 60 N, the
613 estimated value was 3.3 GPa^{-1} . It can be deduced that the observed behavior is likely influenced
614 by the presence of water, which has rather a linear than a power dependence of viscosity on
615 pressure [99]. It can be presumed it is because the amount of water can affect this behavior. On
616 the other hand, the similar trends were published before [72] even with pure PEG200. This

617 means that the behavior of this solution is probably even more complicated and cannot be easily
618 generalized from previous measurements.

619
620 **Fig. 12** Comparison of the evolution of average shear stress and average shear rate in the
621 presence of mean velocity

623 4 Conclusion

624 The properties of the aqueous solution of PEG200 and boric acid were subjected to
625 comprehensive investigation, both subsequent to and throughout the running-in phase. In
626 addition to analyzing the EHL properties of the system and changes in surface topography, the
627 surface/lubricant interface and potential interactions between them were also considered. The
628 following points summarize the most significant changes and properties observed and
629 presumed.

- 630 1. Running-in is characterized not only by a change in the coefficient of friction but also
631 by a change in the rheological properties and hence the thickness of the lubricating layer.
632 The formation of the lubricating layer is also influenced by the boron present in the
633 mixture. Time and low SRR are likely to be the main influences on its formation. The
634 significant role of the contact material was not investigated in detail, but was not
635 apparent during the tests.

- 636 2. The dynamic viscosity of the mixture is influenced by evaporation and other interactions
637 and is even higher after running-in than for pure PEG200. The lubricant solution itself
638 appears to be rather non-Newtonian at high shear rates. Complex behavior and possible
639 interactions with surfaces make the solutions unsuitable for routine predictions of
640 lubricant film thickness. The degree of separation obviously affects the CoF, even when
641 the full (EHL) separation is assumed.
- 642 3. Two regions of significant change in the thickness of the lubricating layer (both central
643 and minimal) were detected during the speed changing process. The adsorption of
644 molecules on the contact surfaces is probably essential aspect of the separation, and thus
645 of achieving a low CoF after the running-in, especially at low speeds.
- 646 4. The thickness and the magnitude and direction of the second change are influenced by
647 the ageing of the mixture. It can be assumed that the change is due to the formation of
648 more complex structures within the lubricant and the transition between two liquid
649 phases of different viscosities.

650

651 **Availability of data and materials**

652 The data supporting the findings of this study are openly available on [Zenodo.org], reference
653 number [14501680] at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14501680>.

654

655 **Competing interest**

656 The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

657

658 **CRedit author contributions**

659 **Tomáš Poláček:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation,
660 Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization. **Martin Kadlec:** Methodology.

661 Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing. **Jiří**
662 **Smilek:** Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision. **Martin Hartl:** Resources,
663 Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Petr Šperka:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources,
664 Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision.

665

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670

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1000 **Graphical abstract**

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